

IMPACT ON WORK LIFE BALANCE OF WORKING WOMEN DURING COVID 19 PANDEMIC

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Abstract

Covid-19 outbreak brings volatility in the globe. The economic condition of all countries, whether it is developed or developing becomes worse. It affected not only the manufacturing, the service sector, but also agriculture and all other allied industries. The covid -19 pandemic was started in China and very soon it was spread all over the world. The country like the USA and the UK, also not escaped from this Pandemic. This happened first time that everything was shut down totally and allows people to stay at home. In India, it came in the month of February, and Government of India took decision of lockdown in the month of March, 24th 2020. With respect to the continuity of business, companies around the world have switched over to online/digital modes of working. In India, various states have been exposed to a situation of complete lockdown which has led employers to think about how to keep their people safe and protect so that to stop this virus spread and also continue their operations effectively. The present paper studies the impact of Covid-19 on working women and tried to find out its effect on their work as well as personal domains. The researcher tried to understand the negative and positive aspects while studying the working women's lives. The telephonic communication and survey conducted through Google form due to the current situation of the Covid -19 Pandemic.

Key Words: *Work Life Balance, Covid-19 Pandemic, lockdown, digital*

Introduction

Work life balance is a method which helps someone to balance their both lives i.e. personal life and work life. It is essential to maintain good WLB to achieve goal and objectives of both lives. One should set their priorities and accordingly manage time for family, health, vacations etc along with making career, business travel etc. Sudden change in world's environment due to Covid 19, the life styles of human being totally changed. The Covid 19 taught us the simplicity of life. The human being becomes shut and animal, birds become free during Covid 19 pandemic. All sectors have been suffering a lot including service, manufacturing, agriculture and so on.

The living styles of people has changed during covid 19, there was no option to any sector to shut their business. The physical work system converted into online work system. The work from home, concept becomes popular in business world. But, moving to online mode of work, create hurdles among the lives of people. It find very difficult to individuals to balance their both lives. It is found that while balancing both lives, specifically women faced many challenges. Hence, the present paper titled 'Impact on work life balance of working women during Covid 19 Pandemic' studied to find out the impact on personal life and work life of working women as well as to find out the factors affected on their lives.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the impact on work life balance of working women during Covid 19 Pandemic
- To find out the factors affected on lives of women.

- To ascertain the challenges faced by working women
- To analyse the factors which supports working women to balance their both lives?

Literature Review

- **Dr.Deshpande(2020)** et.al¹ - The research paper studies the working from home aspects faced by working people which has now penetrated in personal and professional spaces. The main objective of the paper was to understand how people will adapt to change and usage of technology for work, physical and mental adaptability of people in the pandemic phase. The online mode method selected for the study. The responses were collected through Google form as feedback. The paper was concluded with providing suggestions and findings.
- **Aditi Joshi(2020)**² - The Paper studies the management practices with respect to work from home that have changed during covid19 and their impact on the working and psyche of employees. The study focus on whether the employees are satisfied with current situation of working from home and whether there have resulted in their low morale. The main objectives of the studies were to find the factors responsible for dissatisfaction towards work from home and to explore the relationship between work life balance and working from home. A survey was conducted of 308 respondents in India. The chi square test was used to form hypothesis and objectives as well. The researchers found that the dissatisfaction takes place in the mind of employees due to long working hours of working from home which could not able to managed them to balance their both lives i.e. personal life and work life.
- **Bhumika (2020)**³ – This paper aims to attempt to explore the nature of relationship between work life balance and emotional exhaustion expanded by the employed individuals while working from home. Data were collected from 180 working professionals in North India who were working from home during the lockdown. SPSS was used test the hypothesis. The researcher found that the participative leadership could contribute to reduction of work interference with personal life.
- **Dr.Swarnalatha, Dr.Lalitha(2020)**⁴ – The main objectives of the study was to analyse the problems and challenges faced by working women professional in this pandemic situation. The paper was concluded with providing tips to improve working from home in the pandemic. The researchers enlighten on the challenges faced of working women and gender inequality as well.

Challenges faced by working women during Covid 19

¹Dr.Aruna Deshpande, M. S. (2020). Work Life Balance in Phase of Pandemic. *An International Bilingual Peer Reviewed Referred Research Journal* , 10 (38), 229-240.

²Gour, A. J. (2020). A Study of Work Life Balance during Covid 19. *Journal of Critical Reviews* , 7 (11), 4149-4161.

³Bhumika. (2020). Challenges for work life balance during Covid 19 induced nationwide lockdown: Exploring gender difference in emotional exhasution in the Indian setting. *Emerald Insight Gender in Management* .Gour, A. J. (2020). A Study of Work Life Balance during Covid 19. *Journal of Critical Reviews* , 7 (11), 4149-4161.

⁴ Dr. Swarnalatha, D. L. (2020). Work Life Balance in Pandemic and challenges faced by working women professionals. *Mukt Shabd Journal* , IX (V), 6173-6179.

It is found that challenge for women is managing both personal as well as professional without any support from maid because of pandemic doing all day to day activities at home, managing office work, taking care of kids, elderly people etc., really hectic task for women to do all these things. According to ILO, Women globally make up over 70 per cent of workers in health, including those working in care institutions⁵. They are on the front line of the fight against COVID-19. As a result of the pandemic they are facing a double burden: longer shifts at work and additional care work at home. For the almost 100 million female workers in health and care institutions around the world, balancing work and family responsibilities has always been a challenge.

Analysis and Interpretation of the study

Interpretation

It is found that majority of the respondents 52(22.38%) are married and 15(77.62%) are unmarried who responded to the question of marital status.

⁵<https://www.mbaskool.com/business-concepts/human-resources-hr-terms/7045-work-life-balance.html>

Interpretation

It is observed that majority respondents are in the age group of 30(44.78%) 36 to 45 followed by 21(31.34%) are age group of 46-54. Only 15(22.38%) were from age group of 25-35 and one respondents from the age group of 55 and above those have responded to the questionnaire.

⁵<https://www.mbaskool.com/business-concepts/human-resources-hr-terms/7045-work-life-balance.html>

Interpretation

From the above graphical presentation, it is found that majority respondents 42(62.69%) were having less than 10 members in their home whereas 25(37.31%) having members 4 or less than who responded for the questionnaire conducted through Google form.

Interpretation

It is found that majority respondents 43(64.17%) having only one child followed by 19(28.35%) having two children whereas 5(7.46%) having three children and only one respondent who responded that he/she don't have child.

Interpretation

From the above graphical presentation it is found that majority respondents 40(59.70%) faced the problem of **health** during lockdown and working from home followed by 37(55.22%) **continuous use of mobile phone** was one of

obstacle during work from home for office work **always affects** more and they could not managed their work life balance whereas 34(50.75%) **excessive office work** also one of the factors due to which they could not balanced their both lives.

It is also observed that during lockdown and working from home, majority respondents 44(65.68%) faced the problem of **absence domestic help** and hence, they could not able to **pay more attention towards children** due to excessive office work and household activities. In addition to this, **Non support from family members** and **increased expectation from family members** during lockdown were the major factors which sometimes affected on their work life and personal life. Very few respondents said that factors mentioned above were does not affected on their balancing personal as well as work life.

Findings of the Study

- Majority respondents are responded that their health affected during lockdown and working from home.
- Continuous use of mobile phone for office work also increased stress due to which they could not able to balance.
- Increased working hours one of the reason of imbalanced work life of respondents
- Excessive office work and household chores are the function responsible to imbalance work and personal life.
- Absence of domestic help and non support from family members also sometimes affected in balancing work and personal life.
- It find very difficult to fulfil the expectations of each members of family.
- Intensive use of technology, invites physical diseases like body pain, headache and so on.

Recommendations and Suggestions

- One should prepare mentally and physically to face the any uncertain consequences
- Meditation and Yoga need to learn for mental relaxation
- There should clear and specific rules for work from home determined by the organisation.
- As per the demand of hour, one should have knowledge of operation of computer.
- Working hours in case of work from home also specified by the organisation which help the employees to balanced their both lives.
- While assigning responsibilities to female workers specifically in flexi time pattern of employment, organisation should consider the dual responsibilities of women.

Conclusion

Any natural calamities, destroys the nature, human life and assets and so on. The covid 19 pandemic is one of the manmade calamity came in India in the month of January and later started to spread to all over the India. Covid 19 pandemic made every individual to lock themselves in cage. The human being trapped in cage and animals got freedom to move freely. The lockdown in India declared by the Government in the month of March and it was continued till December, which was turning point to change the life of human being. Many of loses their job and become unemployed.

Those who managed to retained their job, became stressful due to imbalance work life. Work from home became popular concept during covid 19 pandemic. But it is observed that working from home create lot of problems in the life of employees especially female employees. It find very difficult to manage both the lives to women workers. Absence of domestic help and non cooperation of family members were two important factors due to which they could

not able to manage their both lives. In addition to this, increased working hours and continuous use of computer/ laptop majority female workers faced the health problems like increases their spectacle number, spondylosis, migraine etc. Hence,, there should be clear and specific standard rules and regulation prescribed by the organisation for the employees to work from home.